

A crystal structure analysis⁵ of a compound of ethyleneglycol with sodiumbenzoylacetate has shown that the glycol molecule, while coordinated, is not chelated but bridging two sodium atoms. Similar structure is suggested for these alkali metal complexes in view of the similarity of the compounds.

References

1. N. V. SIDGWICK and F. M. BREWER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 2379.
2. A. K. BANERJEE, A. J. LAYTON, R. S. NYHOLM and MARY R. TRUTER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, (A) 1969, 2536.
3. A. GRUN and E. BOEDECKER, *Ber.*, 1910, 43, 1051.
4. T. V. HEALY, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1968, 30, 1025.
5. A. J. KOLOMBOS, D. BRIGHT, G. H. W. MILLBURN, R. S. NYHOLM and MARY R. TRUTER, *J. Chem. Soc. (D)*, 1970, 1, 49.

Complex Formation of Lanthanum with β -Resorcylic Acid

S. S. DHINDSA, R. C. SHARMA, and D. N. BHARGAVA

P. G. Chemistry Department, Government College, Kota (Rajasthan)

Manuscript received 26 December 1975, accepted 9 March 1976

β -RESORCYLIC acid (H_3RSA) figures prominently in the discussion of hydroxy carboxylic acids and provides two possible co-ordination sites, viz, -COOH and -OH groups, which have attracted the attention of many workers to explore the interaction of this acid with many metal ions¹⁻⁶. A close examination of the existing literature reveals the absence of any study on this system. Hence the present investigations have been carried out.

Experimental

AnalaR (B. D. H.) reagents sodium hydroxide, lanthanum nitrate and Fluka's β -resorcylic acid, were used. A cambridge pH meter was used to determine the H^+ concentration of the reaction mixtures.

Conductance measurements were carried out by a conductometer (WTW Leitfähigkeitsmesser, type LBR, made in Germany) with magic eye as a visual indicator.

The experimental procedure consisted of potentiometric and conductometric titrations of ligand in the absence and presence of Lanthanum nitrate against standard alkali.

Results and Discussion

The appearance of inflections and breaks after the addition of one and two moles of alkali per mole of ligand (Fig. 1, curves 1 and 1') correspond respectively to the neutralisation of carboxyl and *p*-phenolic groups.

Fig. 1. Potentiometric and conductometric titration curves of H_3RSA in the absence & presence of $La(III)$ with $0.1M$ $NaOH$. Curves 1 & 1': $5 \times 10^{-3}M$ H_3RSA ; curves 2 & 2': $5 \times 10^{-3}M$ $H_3RSA + 5 \times 10^{-3}M$ $La(III)$; curves 3 & 3': $1 \times 10^{-2}M$ $H_3RSA + 5 \times 10^{-3}M$ $La(III)$.

When 1 : 1 mixture of ligand and metal is titrated against standard alkali (curve-2) no complex formation was observed till pH 7.0, but above this pH, the affinity of ligand for metal increases, as a result of which a decrease in the corresponding pH values is observed. An inflection at m=4 corresponds to the formation of 1 : 1 hydroxo complex and neutralisation of *p*-OH group of the ligand. The reaction may be represented as :

2 : 1 mixture of ligand and metal (curve-3) against standard alkali indicates two inflections at m=2 and m=6. The first corresponds to the neutralisation of -COOH groups and the second inflection corresponds to the formation of 1 : 1 hydroxo-complex and neutralisation of *p*-OH groups of the ligand.

The precipitation begins to appear above pH 7.0

The composition was further confirmed by conductometric titrations. The breaks at m=1 and m=4 in the 1 : 1 mixture of ligand and metal against standard alkali (curve 2'), clearly indicates the neutralisation of -COOH

group of the acid and formation of 1 : 1 hydroxo complex in accordance with the equations 3 and 4.

The breaks at $m=2$ and $m=6$ in the 2 : 1 mixture of ligand and metal (curve 3') further confirms the above formation.

The present investigation clearly reveals the formation of 1 : 1 hydroxo complex above pH 7.0.

References

1. S. K. K. JATKAR and B. N. MATTOO, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 30, 775.
2. ANIL K. MUKHERJEE and B. R. SANT, *Naturwiss.*, 1959, 46, 74.
3. M. L. N. REDDI and V. V. SESHAIHAH, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1964, 2, 34.
4. M. N. DESAI and B. M. DESAI, *Current Sci.*, 1965, 34, 244.
5. M. N. DESAI and B. M. DESAI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 42, 643.
6. S. S. DUBBY and S. S. DHINDSA, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1970, 32, 543.

Studies on 6-Heteropoly Vanadomolybdate

SALIL KUMAR ROY and G. C. BHATTACHARYA

Department of Chemistry, Ranchi University, Ranchi-8.

Manuscript received 9 February 1976, accepted 11 March 1976

A few heteropoly vanadates have been reported^{1,2} but with the exception of 12-vanadophosphate anion, none of them has been well characterised^{3,4}. The present short communication deals with the preparation, characterisation and X-ray crystal diffraction studies of a new 1 : 6 heteropoly complex of vanadium with molybdenum as the heteroatom.

Water solutions of molybdic acid and potassium metavanadate were taken in the molar ratio of 1 : 12 and refluxed for nearly 4 hr. The solution was left in atmosphere for a few hours and then crystallised under vacuum when small needle shaped red crystals came out which were recrystallised thrice from hot water. The complete analysis of the compound was done by chemical and colorimetric analysis, from which the percentage of potassium, vanadium and molybdenum were found to be 10.62, 27.88, 8.70 against the theoretical calculated values 10.70, 27.99, 8.78. The percentage of water together with oxygen was calculated by difference which came to 37.434. From these percentage composition data the ratio between Mo : V came to 1 : 6, which agreed with the formula $K_8 [MoV_6O_{19}] 11H_2O$. The representation of the formula was according to the views of Keggin⁵.

X-ray Crystallographic data and determination of molecular weight : A single crystal of the compound was mounted along its longer dimension : a axis. The oscillation photographs did not show mx, my and mm

symmetry. Zero level, first level and second level Weissenberg photographs were taken. The absence of Weissenberg photographs of OKO for $K \neq 2n$ and hol for $K \neq 2n$ identified the space group as P_{21}/C . The angle was determined by the method of 'level offsets'. The final values of cell dimensions are : $a = 9.42 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 15.38 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 10.12 \text{ \AA}$ and $\beta = 105^\circ$, hence the system is monoclinic. The volume 'V' per unit cell was calculated to be 1416.18 \AA^3 . The number of molecules per unit cell 'Z' was fixed to be 2. The observed density measured by flotation method $\rho_{obs} = 2.53 \text{ gml}^{-1}$. From the relation $\rho_{obs} = \frac{1.66MZ}{V}$, the molecular weight 'M' of the compound came to 1081 against the theoretical value 1092.95, calculated from its stoichiometric formula. This definitely shows that the compound is monomeric.

Acknowledgement

We are grateful to the authorities of Planning and Development Division, Sindri, Bihar, for their active help in collecting the X-ray photographs.

References

1. O. W. GIBBS, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1884, 5, 374 ; *Proc. Amer. Acad.*, 1883, 18, 232.
2. L. MILCH, C. FRIEDHEIM, H. VON EULER-CHAPLIN, F. TOGGENBURG and A. ISENBERG, "A Comprehensive Treatise on Inorganic and Theoretical Chemistry", Longmans, Green & Co, London, 1952, Vol. IX, p. 780.
3. A. ROSENHEIM and M. PIECK, *Z. Anorg. Chem.*, 1916, 98, 223 ; P. SOUCHAY and S. DUPOIS, *Ann. Chim.*, 1948, 3, 88.
4. W. B. DALE, JANET. M. BUCKLEY and M. T. POPE, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, 2-A, 301.
5. J. F. KEGGIN, *Proc. Royal. Soc.*, 1934, A, 144.

Determination of Oxidizing Powers of Tinperoxychromate and its Water Decomposition Product

S. P. S. JADON and D. S. RATHOR

Chemical Laboratory, Shri Varshney College, Aligarh

Manuscript received 9 December 1974, revised 8 July 1975, accepted 15 July 1975

RIESENFIELD and Coworkers¹ have shown the existence of two classes of peroxychromate, blue and red, derived respectively from $HCrO_5$ and H_3CrO_5 . Raynold and Reedy², Klemm and Werth³, Beltron Martinez and Rea⁴ have prepared the perchromate of calcium, potassium and magnesium respectively.

Schwarz and Giese⁵, Prakash and Rai⁶ on the basis of their studies formulated chromium peroxychromate as CrO_4 and $Cr_2(Cr_2O_{10})_8$ respectively.

The present paper consists of the study of tinperoxychromate and its water decomposition product. It throws light on the constitution of tinperoxychromate and thus explains the formation of decomposition product.